
 ON SUMS OF CONSECUTIVE TRIANGULAR NUMBERS

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Abstract

By a *triangular number*, we mean one of the numbers $\Delta_n := \frac{1}{2}n(n+1)$, for $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. In a recent *Math Horizons* note, Matthew McMullen suggested studying triangular sums of consecutive triangular numbers. In other words, one seeks solutions to equations of the form

$$\Delta_n + \dots + \Delta_{n+(k-1)} = \Delta_m.$$

McMullen classified the solutions when $2 \leq k \leq 5$; there are no solutions when $k = 4$, while in the other cases, there are infinitely many solutions. He asked if there is a value of $k > 4$ for which there are no solutions. Here we show that there are solutions for every square value of k larger than 4, but that for almost all values of k (asymptotically 100%), there are no solutions.

1. Introduction

By a *triangular number*, we mean a member of the sequence

$$\Delta_n := \frac{1}{2}n(n+1), \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

(Some authors include 0 as a triangular number; for our purposes it is convenient to leave 0 out.) Triangular numbers feature prominently in the history of number

theory. Probably the most famous example is the July 10, 1796 entry in Gauss’s mathematical diary (see [4]):

$$\text{ETPHKA! num} = \Delta + \Delta + \Delta.$$

Expressed in less telegraphic notation: Every positive integer is a sum of three triangular numbers, where 0 is allowed. About 30 years later (1828), in a treatise on elliptic functions, Legendre published a simple formula for the number of representations of a nonnegative integer n as a sum of four triangular numbers (again, allowing 0): For every $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$,

$$\#\{(x, y, z, w) \in \mathbb{N}_0 : \frac{x(x+1)}{2} + \frac{y(y+1)}{2} + \frac{z(z+1)}{2} + \frac{w(w+1)}{2} = n\} = \sigma(2n+1),$$

where $\sigma(m) = \sum_{d|m} d$.

In a recent note in *Math Horizons* [7], McMullen suggested investigating the solutions to equations of the form

$$\Delta_n + \cdots + \cdots + \Delta_{n+(k-1)} = \Delta_m. \tag{1}$$

In other words: When is a sum of consecutive triangular numbers also triangular? McMullen found all solutions for $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$; when $k = 4$ there is no solution, while in the three other cases, there are infinitely many solutions, corresponding to solutions to certain Pell equations. The note ends with the following question:

Every value of k except $k = 4$ that I looked at yields at least one valid solution. Is there a $k > 4$ where our problem has no solution?

We prove two theorems concerning solutions to (1). First, we show that $k = 4$ is the only square value for which (1) lacks solutions.

Theorem 1. *Let $k > 4$ be a square. Then (1) has solutions. In other words, there do exist k consecutive triangular numbers that add up to a triangular number.*

In the opposite direction, we show that for almost all values of k , there are no solutions to (1). Thus, the answer to McMullen’s question is a definite YES !

Theorem 2. *Let $K(x)$ denote the number of integers $2 \leq k \leq x$ for which (1) has solutions. Then $K(x) = O(x/(\log x)^{1/2})$. In particular, $K(x)/x \rightarrow 0$, so that the set of k for which (1) is solvable has asymptotic density 0.*

Theorem 1 obviously implies that $K(x) \gg \sqrt{x}$. There is a large gap between \sqrt{x} and $x/(\log x)^{1/2}$, and it is natural to ask which of these functions is closer to the truth about $K(x)$. We believe it is the latter; indeed, we conclude the paper with a heuristic argument suggesting that $K(x) \gg x/(\log x)^{3/2}$.

2. When k is a Square: Proof of Theorem 1

Elementary manipulations show that (1) is equivalent to

$$(2m + 1)^2 - k(2n + k)^2 = \frac{(k - 1)(k^2 + k - 3)}{3}. \tag{2}$$

Up to this point we have not used that k is a square. But if we now let $k = a^2$, then (2) becomes

$$(2m + 1 - a(2n + a^2))(2m + 1 + a(2n + a^2)) = \frac{(a - 1)(a + 1)(a^4 + a^2 - 3)}{3}. \tag{3}$$

(This factorization is noted already in [7].) To prove Theorem 1, we must show that (3) has a solution in positive integers m, n . We consider separately the cases when a is even vs. when a is odd.

2.1. When a is Even

Since k is even, we have $a \geq 3$. Choosing

$$m = \frac{a^2(a^2 - 2)(a^2 + 2)}{12}, \quad n = \frac{a(a - 2)(a^3 + 2a^2 + 4a + 2)}{12},$$

the first factor on the left-hand side of (3) is 1, while the second factor is equal to the right-hand side of (3); thus, (3) holds. Since a is even, both numerators in the expressions defining m and n are multiples of 4. Taking cases for $a \pmod 3$, we find that both numerators are also multiples of 3. Thus, m and n are integers. Finally, since $a \geq 3$, one sees easily that $m, n > 0$.

2.2. When a is Odd

In this case, the left-hand side of (3) is a product of two even numbers. Dividing by 2 leads to the system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} m - an + \frac{1 - a^3}{2} &= d \\ m + an + \frac{1 + a^3}{2} &= d', \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

for some positive integers d and d' satisfying

$$dd' = \frac{(a - 1)(a + 1)(a^4 + a^2 - 3)}{12}. \tag{5}$$

We subdivide this case further according to the value of a modulo 3:

- When $a \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, both $d = \frac{a+1}{2}$ and $d' = \frac{(a-1)(a^4+a^2-3)}{6}$ are positive integers, and (5) holds. Solving (4) with these values of d, d' leads to

$$m = \frac{a^2(a-1)(a^2+1)}{12}, \quad n = \frac{(a+2)(a-3)(a^2+1)}{12}.$$

Reasoning as in the case of even a , we find that m, n are positive integers.

- If $a \equiv 0$ or $2 \pmod{3}$, then $d = \frac{a-1}{2}$ and $d' = \frac{(a+1)(a^4+a^2-3)}{6}$ are positive integers. These choices lead to

$$m = \frac{a^5 + a^4 + a^3 + a^2 - 12}{12}, \quad n = \frac{(a+3)(a-2)(a^2+1)}{12}.$$

Again, one checks easily that m, n are positive integers.

3. Equation (1) Usually Has No Solution: Proof of Theorem 2

We require the following lemma.

Lemma 3. *Let $q > 3$ be a prime number. Suppose that $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ is such that*

- (i) k is not a square modulo q ,
- (ii) $q \parallel k^2 + k - 3$.

Then there are no k consecutive triangular numbers that add up to a triangular number.

Proof. Assume for a contradiction that k satisfies (i) and (ii) but that (1) has a solution. Then there are positive integers m, n satisfying (2). Let $x = 2m + 1$ and $y = 2n + k$, so that $x^2 - ky^2$ represents the left-hand side of (2). Condition (i) guarantees that k is not congruent to 1 modulo q . Thus, q is coprime to $k - 1$. Condition (ii) now implies that

$$q \parallel \frac{(k-1)(k^2+k-3)}{3} = x^2 - ky^2.$$

If q divides one of x or y , then q divides the other, since $x^2 \equiv ky^2 \pmod{q}$ and q is coprime to k . But then $q^2 \mid x^2 - ky^2$, a contradiction. So q is coprime to both x and y , forcing $(x/y)^2 \equiv k \pmod{q}$. This contradicts (i). \square

We will also use the following consequence of the Chebotarev density theorem (or the weaker Frobenius density theorem); a readable modern reference is [8].

Proposition 4. *Suppose that $f(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ is monic and irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , with $\deg f(x) = n$. Let L be the splitting field of $f(x)$ over \mathbb{Q} . Fix a partition $\langle k_1, \dots, k_r \rangle$ of n (that is, a tuple of positive integers $k_1 \geq k_2 \geq \dots \geq k_r$ with $k_1 + \dots + k_r = n$). Let δ be the proportion of elements of $\text{Gal}(L/\mathbb{Q})$ which, when viewed as permutations on the roots of $f(x)$, have cycle type $\langle k_1, \dots, k_r \rangle$. For all but finitely many primes p , the polynomial $f(x)$ factors as a product of distinct monic irreducible polynomials modulo p , and δ is the proportion of primes for which these irreducibles have degrees k_1, \dots, k_r .*

In Proposition 4, “proportion of primes” is meant in the same sense as in the Chebotarev density theorem. The version of that theorem proved by Artin in [1] implies that the number of primes $p \leq x$ for which f factors mod p into irreducibles of degrees k_1, \dots, k_r is

$$\delta \cdot \pi(x) + O(x/(\log x)^2). \tag{6}$$

(In (6), the implied constant is allowed to depend on f , which we view as fixed.)

Lemma 5. *Let \mathcal{A} be the set of primes p for which the polynomial $g(x) = x^2 + x - 3$ has two distinct roots mod p , neither of which is a square mod p , and let \mathcal{B} be the set of primes p for which $g(x)$ has two distinct roots mod p , exactly one of which is a square mod p . The proportion of primes in \mathcal{A} is $\frac{1}{8}$, while the proportion of primes in \mathcal{B} is $\frac{1}{4}$.*

Proof. Let $f(x) = x^4 + x^2 - 3$. Then f is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} , the splitting field L of f over \mathbb{Q} has degree 8, we have $\text{Gal}(L/\mathbb{Q}) \cong D_4$, and under an appropriate numbering of the roots of f , the Galois group of L/\mathbb{Q} can be identified with the subgroup

$$\{(1), (1324), (12)(34), (1423), (34), (13)(24), (12), (14)(23)\}$$

of S_4 . All of this follows immediately from the easily-checkable criteria of [6] concerning quartics $x^4 + ax^2 + b$; see in particular that paper’s Theorems 2 and 3.

Suppose that $p \in \mathcal{A}$. Thus, g splits over \mathbb{F}_p ,

$$g(x) = (x - \theta_1)(x - \theta_2) \quad \text{for some } \theta_1 \neq \theta_2 \in \mathbb{F}_p.$$

Moreover,

$$f(x) = g(x^2) = (x^2 - \theta_1)(x^2 - \theta_2),$$

where the two quadratic factors are distinct and irreducible over \mathbb{F}_p . Conversely, suppose that g splits over \mathbb{F}_p and that f factors as a product of distinct monic irreducibles of degree 2. Then the roots of g , say θ_1 and θ_2 , must be nonsquares in \mathbb{F}_p ; otherwise, $x^2 - \theta_1$ or $x^2 - \theta_2$ will contribute a linear factor to f . Thus, using Prob to denote proportions of primes (the notation chosen to suggest probability), we see that

$$\text{Prob}(p \in \mathcal{A}) = \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 2, 2 \rangle).$$

(When we write “ f factors as $\langle k_1, \dots, k_r \rangle$ ”, we mean that f factors as a product of distinct monic irreducibles of degrees k_1, \dots, k_r .)

We may rewrite the right-hand side of the last display as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits}) - \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 4 \rangle) - \\ & \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 2, 1, 1 \rangle) - \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 1, 1, 1, 1 \rangle). \end{aligned}$$

The first subtracted term is 0; if g has the root $\theta \pmod p$, then $x^2 - \theta$ is a factor of f over \mathbb{F}_p , so f cannot be irreducible. The final two subtracted terms are unchanged if we omit the condition that g splits. Indeed, f factoring as $\langle 2, 1, 1 \rangle$ or $\langle 1, 1, 1, 1 \rangle$ implies that f has a root θ ; then f also has the root $-\theta$, and as long as $q \neq 3$, those two roots are distinct. Hence, $x^2 - \theta^2 \mid f(x) = g(x^2)$. But this implies that θ^2 is a root of g . Since g is a quadratic with a root, g splits. (The roots are distinct since we are assuming $f(x) = g(x^2)$ factors as a product of distinct monic irreducibles.) So by Proposition 4 together with our determination of the Galois group of f , these final two probabilities are $\frac{2}{8}$ and $\frac{1}{8}$, respectively. Finally, the probability that g splits mod p is $\frac{1}{2}$, by applying Proposition 4 to g . We conclude that

$$\text{Prob}(p \in \mathcal{A}) = \frac{1}{2} - 0 - \frac{2}{8} - \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{8}.$$

A similar argument works to determine $\text{Prob}(p \in \mathcal{B})$. Here it is easy to see that

$$\text{Prob}(p \in \mathcal{B}) = \text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 2, 1, 1 \rangle).$$

But as noted at the end of the last paragraph,

$$\text{Prob}(g \text{ splits \& } f \text{ factors as } \langle 2, 1, 1 \rangle) = \text{Prob}(f \text{ factors as } \langle 2, 1, 1 \rangle) = \frac{2}{8} = \frac{1}{4}.$$

This completes the proof. □

We are now ready to prove Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. We use \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} with the same meanings as in Lemma 5. Let p be a prime in \mathcal{A} . The conditions (i) and (ii) of Lemma 3 will then be satisfied for all k in $2p - 2$ residue classes modulo p^2 . Indeed, if r is either of the two roots of $x^2 + x - 3$ modulo p — both of which are nonsquares mod p by assumption — and $k \equiv r \pmod p$, then $q \parallel k^2 + k - 3$ unless k is congruent modulo p^2 to the unique lift of $r \pmod p$ to a root of $x^2 + x - 3$ modulo p^2 . Similarly, for each $p \in \mathcal{B}$, the conditions (i) and (ii) of Lemma 3 are satisfied for all k in $p - 1$ residue classes modulo p^2 . But if k is counted by $K(x)$, then k does not satisfy (i) and (ii) for any p . In particular, considering for now only those $p \in \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$ not exceeding $z := (\log x)^{1/2}$, we see that k is confined to N residue classes modulo $P := \prod_{p \leq z} p^2$, where

$$\frac{N}{P} = \prod_{\substack{p \leq z \\ p \in \mathcal{A}}} \left(1 - \frac{2p - 2}{p^2}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \leq z \\ p \in \mathcal{B}}} \left(1 - \frac{p - 1}{p^2}\right)$$

Continuing, we note that we may ignore the contribution to $K(x)$ from k satisfying

$$p^2 \mid k^2 + k - 3 \quad \text{for some prime } p > z. \tag{7}$$

Indeed, for each prime p , there are at most two roots of $k^2 + k - 3$ modulo p . As long as $p \neq 13$, each root mod p lifts to a unique mod p^2 , by Hensel’s lemma. Thus, if $p^2 \mid k^2 + k - 3$, then k is confined to a certain two residue classes modulo p^2 , and the corresponding number of $k \leq x$ is at most $2x/p^2 + 2$. Also, if $k \leq x$ and $p^2 \mid k^2 + k - 3$, we certainly have $p \leq 2x$ (for large x). Thus, the total number of $k \leq x$ for which (7) holds is

$$\leq \sum_{z < p \leq 2x} \left(\frac{2x}{p^2} + 2 \right) \ll x \sum_{m > z} \frac{1}{m^2} + \pi(2x) \ll \frac{x}{(\log x)^{1/2}}.$$

Since our goal is to show $K(x) = O(x/(\log x)^{1/2})$, this contribution is acceptable.

Suppose now that $p > z$. If $p \in \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B}$, and $p \mid k^2 + k - 3$ where k is a nonsquare modulo p , then either $p^2 \mid k^2 + k - 3$ — in which case, p was counted in the last paragraph already — or conditions (i) and (ii) of Lemma 3 hold. Thus, if k is counted by $K(x)$ and k was not accounted for in the last paragraph, then k avoids 2 residue classes mod p for those $p \in \mathcal{A}$ and one residue classes mod p for those $p \in \mathcal{B}$.

Let $R \pmod P$ denote any one of the N residue classes modulo P not eliminated in the first paragraph of the proof. We may assume that $0 \leq R < P$. Suppose k is counted by $K(x)$, that k does not satisfy (7), and that $k \equiv R \pmod P$. Then $k = Pu + R$, where $0 \leq u \leq x/P$. By our work in the last paragraph, k , and hence u , avoids two residue classes modulo each prime $p \in \mathcal{A} \cap (z, x]$ and one residue class modulo each prime $p \in \mathcal{B} \cap (z, x]$. Applying Brun’s sieve, the number of choices of u , and hence k , is

$$\ll \frac{x}{P} \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ z < p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{2}{p} \right) \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ z < p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right).$$

(This follows from the first half Theorem 2.2 of [5]; the parameter “ A ” in that result can be taken to be 2, since the height x up to which we sieve satisfies $x \leq (x/P)^2$ for large enough x .) Now summing on possible R s, we see that the total number of values of k encountered this way is

$$\ll x \frac{N}{P} \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ z < p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{2}{p} \right) \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ z < p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right).$$

Turning attention to the factor $\frac{N}{P}$, we note that $1 - \frac{2p-2}{p^2} \leq (1 - \frac{2}{p})(1 + O(1/p^2))$, and $1 - \frac{p-1}{p^2} \leq (1 - \frac{1}{p})(1 + O(1/p^2))$. Since $\prod_p (1 + O(1/p^2)) = O(1)$, we deduce that

$\frac{N}{P} \ll \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ p \leq z}} \left(1 - \frac{2}{p}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ p \leq z}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)$. Hence, the right-hand side of the last display is

$$\ll x \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{2}{p}\right) \prod_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ p \leq x}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right).$$

The right-hand side of this new display does not exceed

$$x \exp \left(-2 \sum_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ p \leq x}} \frac{1}{p} - \sum_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ p \leq x}} \frac{1}{p} \right).$$

We finish by substituting in the estimates

$$\sum_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{A} \\ p \leq x}} \frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{8} \log \log x + O(1) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{\substack{p \in \mathcal{B} \\ p \leq x}} \frac{1}{p} = \frac{1}{4} \log \log x + O(1);$$

these follow from Lemma 5, the estimate (6), and partial summation. □

Remark. One can show that $K(x)/x \rightarrow 0$ without using the Chebotarev (or Frobenius) density theorem. It is not difficult to prove directly that the primes $p \in \mathcal{B}$ with $p > 3$ are precisely those with $\left(\frac{-3}{p}\right) = -1$ and $\left(\frac{13}{p}\right) = 1$. Quadratic reciprocity, along with a sufficiently strong form of Dirichlet’s theorem, then implies that the proportion of primes in \mathcal{B} is $\frac{1}{4}$. Sieving only by the primes in \mathcal{B} in the above proof is sufficient to yield the estimate $K(x) = O(x/(\log x)^{1/4})$.

4. A Heuristic Lower Bound on $K(x)$

We find it plausible that the following conditions should hold simultaneously for $\gg x/(\log x)^{3/2}$ primes $p \leq x$:

- (i) $p \equiv 7 \pmod{24}$,
- (ii) $p^2 + p - 3$ is not divisible by any prime q for which $p \pmod q$ is a nonsquare,
- (iii) the real quadratic field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{p})$ has class number 1.

Examples of primes p satisfying these conditions are $p = 7, 31, 103$, and 127.

The same kind of sieve-based reasoning underlying the proof of Theorem 2 suggests that (i) and (ii) hold for $\gg \pi(x)/(\log x)^{1/2} \gg x/(\log x)^{3/2}$ primes $p \leq x$.¹ The Cohen–Lenstra heuristics [2, 3] suggest that (iii), by itself, holds for a positive

¹Using the sieve, one can show unconditionally that there are $\ll x/(\log x)^{3/2}$ primes $p \leq x$ for which (i) and (ii) hold, and that there are $\gg x/(\log x)^{3/2}$ primes $p \leq x$ that satisfy (i) and a weak form of (ii), where (ii) is required only for q up to a small power of x .

proportion — roughly 75.45% — of primes p . Lacking any reason for believing the contrary, we believe that a positive proportion of the p surviving (i) and (ii) should also satisfy (iii). Indeed, we suspect that (i) and (ii) are statistically independent of (iii). This is supported by the computational evidence; for instance, of the 9824 primes $p \equiv 7 \pmod{24}$ not exceeding 10^6 , 4417 of them satisfy conditions (i) and (ii), and 3451 satisfy condition (iii). The ratio $\frac{3451}{4417}$ is $\approx 78.13\%$. For comparison, 61320 of the 78498 primes $p \leq 10^6$ satisfy (iii), and $\frac{61320}{78498} \approx 78.12\%$.

Now suppose that p satisfies (i)–(iii). Let $k = p$. We will show that (1) has a solution by finding positive integers m, n satisfying (2). Hence, k will be counted by $K(x)$, and the lower bound $K(x) \gg x/(\log x)^{3/2}$ “follows”.

For notational convenience, we let

$$T = \frac{(k-1)(k^2+k-3)}{3}.$$

Let q be any odd prime dividing T . Our assumptions imply that k is a square modulo q , and so q splits or ramifies in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{k})$. When $q = 2$, we have that $2 \parallel T$. The prime 2 ramifies in $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{k})$ since the field discriminant is the even integer $4k$. So every prime dividing T is split or ramified.

The ring $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{k}]$ is the full ring of integers of the class number 1 field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{k})$. Thus, for each prime q dividing T , we can choose an element $x_q + y_q\sqrt{k} \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{k}]$ with $N(x_q + y_q\sqrt{k}) = \pm q$. Working modulo 8 shows that we must have

$$N(x_2 + y_2\sqrt{k}) = 2,$$

(i.e., the plus sign must hold), and that for each odd prime q dividing T ,

$$N(x_q + y_q\sqrt{k}) = \chi(q)q,$$

where $\chi(\cdot)$ is the nontrivial Dirichlet character modulo 4. (Thus, $\chi(q) = \pm 1$ with the sign chosen to make $\chi(q) \equiv q \pmod{4}$.) Define

$$\alpha = \prod_{q^\alpha \parallel T} (x_q + y_q\sqrt{k})^\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{k}].$$

Then

$$N\alpha = T \cdot \chi(T/2).$$

It is not difficult to check that since $k \equiv 7 \pmod{24}$, we have $T/2 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and so in fact $N\alpha = T$.

Changing the signs of the components of α if necessary, we obtain an element

$$\beta = s + t\sqrt{k}$$

with norm T and $s, t \geq 0$. Since $s^2 - kt^2 = T \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $k \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, we must have that s, t are odd. Thus, we can write $s = 2m + 1$ and $t = 2n + k$ for

some integers m, n . Then

$$(2m + 1)^2 - k(2n + k)^2 = T,$$

which is (2). However, we do not know that m, n are positive here; for that, we need $s > 1$ and $t > k$. To ensure this, we replace β with $\beta\epsilon^m$, where ϵ is the fundamental unit of $\mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{k}]$, and m is large enough to give the needed inequalities on s and t .

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